

Damage rating

Virulence of *N. virescens* colonies on resistant rices, IRRI. For each cultivar, means with a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

TAPL 796. None were virulent to ASD7 or ASD8.

Results indicate that *N. virescens* can adapt to resistant varieties in the

greenhouse. This also may happen in the field. With this result, the stability of resistance of a variety in the field can be predicted. The cross virulence observed

on some colonies suggests that *N. virescens* can adapt to varieties with different genes for resistance. ☞

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

HYBRID RICE

Wei You 64 — an early duration hybrid for China

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In 1979, several elite rice lines with multiple disease and insect resistance were introduced in China through the China-IRRI collaborative program on hybrid rice. They were intended for use as improved restorers for hybrid rice development.

In 1980, test crosses were made with the cytoplasmic-genetic male sterile line V20A in China and at IRRI. Evaluation of nursery results identified IR9761-19-1 as an effective restorer. The F₁, V20A/IR9761-19-1, was more productive than its male parent.

In 1981 dry season, the lines were again crossed at IRRI and the F₁ was evaluated at four sites in Hunan and at IRRI in wet season. At all sites, fertility restoration was complete and the hybrid matured earlier than the restorer.

Chinese scientists purified the restorer line and produced enough seeds of IR9761-19-1 with plant selection 64

(IR9761-19-1-64) to evaluate in 1981 replicated yield trials. The results were encouraging. In 1981-82 winter season, hybrid seeds were grown on 3.3 ha on Hainan Island. Mean seed yield was 2.2 t/ha. In 1982 second season, the combination was reevaluated in replicated yield trials and on-farm trials in Hunan and compared to the commercial hybrid Wei You 6 (V20A/IR26). V20A/IR9761-19-1-64 matured 2 wk earlier and yielded about 1 t/ha more than Wei You 6 (Table 1).

Seed was multiplied in Hunan and Hainan and 6,500 ha of the new hybrid was grown in summer 1983 in Hunan,

Guangdong, Jiangsi, Zhejiang, and Fukien. In 1984, the hybrid was named Wei You 64 and was planted on 0.26 million ha in China.

Wei You 64 yielded about 1 t/ha more than conventionally bred Xian Ai Zhao 9 in national yield trials in the South Yangtze Valley (Table 2). It matured in 124 d. Wei You 64 yielded the same as Wei You 6 but matured 12 d earlier (Table 3). Its short duration allows a second crop planting as late as 1 Aug without significant yield loss. If planted that late, Wei You 6 yields only 3 t/ha. Highest yield of Wei You 64 in China has been 11.3 t/ha.

Wei You 64 is resistant to blast, bacterial blight, brown planthopper (BPH), and green leafhopper and moderately resistant to yellow dwarf virus in China. It yields more seed (1.5-2.5 t/ha) than Wei You 6 (1-2 t/ha) because its male parent produces more pollen. Wei You 64 is susceptible to sheath blight, and therefore unsuitable for waterlogged soils. It is moderately resistant to lodging.

Table 1. Performance of V20A/IR9761-1-19-1-64 (Wei You 64) and Wei You 6 in regional yield trials (second crop) in Hunan, China, 1982.

Hybrid	Trials (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	Growth duration (d)	Productivity (kg/ha per d)
V20A/IR9761-19-1-64	17	6.1	101	57
Wei You 6	17	5.1	125	41

Table 2. Performance of Wei You 64 and Xian Ai Zhao 9 in national yield trials (first crop) in China, 1984.

Hybrid	Trials (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	Growth duration (d)	Productivity (kg/ha per d)
Wei You 64	14	1.7	124	62
Xian Ai Zhao 9	14	6.8	119	57

Table 3. Performance of Wei You 64 and Wei You 6 in national yield trials (one crop) in China, 1984.

Hybrid	Trials (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	Growth duration (d)	Productivity (kg/ha per d)
Wei You 64	10	1.8	124	63
Wei You 6	10	1.9	136	58

V20A/IR9761-19-1 also has shown promise in trials in Indonesia, India, and Korea. At IRRI, however, its yields are

limited by tungro, ragged stunt, and grassy stunt 2, and by BPH biotype 2. *ℓ*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

DROUGHT TOLERANCE

Developing closely related rice lines with different drought-induced abscisic acid (ABA) accumulation

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ABA is a plant hormone that mediates plant responses to drought stress. It causes stomata to close, thus reducing transpirational water losses. Differences in the ability of plants to accumulate ABA could affect their ability to withstand drought.

To objectively evaluate the consequences of differences in drought-induced ABA accumulation (DIAA) on survival or yield ability during drought, genetic stocks with contrasting DIAA but similar characteristics are required. We screened several rices for DIAA using a test in which leaves were

Characteristics of F₄ plants of two rice crosses and plants of the parental genotypes. ^a

	ABA content (ng/g fresh weight)	Leaf fresh weight (mg)	Plant height at maturity (cm)	Days to panicle emergence from sowing
<i>IR20/63-83</i>				
Low-ABA selections (n=12)	391	455	64.8	90.2
High-ABA selections (n=21)	814***	398 ^{ns}	17.9*	91.0 ^{ns}
63-83(n=6)	428	629	100.5	85.3
IR20 (n=6)	909***	190***	41.8***	85.0 ^{ns}
<i>IR20/IR36</i>				
Low-ABA selections (n=15)	606	206	54.2	84.2
High-ABA selections (n=22)	844***	181 ^{ns}	52.2 ^{ns}	83.5 ^{ns}
IR36 (n=3)	512	185	51.3	86.7
IR20 (n=3)	919*	110***	38.1**	93.0 ^{ns}

^a Plants were grown in a glasshouse at Cambridge, U. K. *, ** and *** indicate significant differences at $P < 0.05$, 0.01 and 0.001, respectively, between low- and high-ABA selections and between parental genotypes; ns = not significant. ^b Leaf six for IR20/63-83 and leaf five for IR20/IR36.

detached and rapidly water-stressed. ABA concentrations were determined in

leaf extracts using a gas-liquid chromatograph fitted with a pulse-